

Pitchfork Domination and its inverse in an undirected graph $G_{m,n}$

Dr.Syeda Asma Kauser^{#1}, Dr.Mashaer Alsaedi^{*2}

[#] Associate professor, Department of Mathematics
Anwarul Uloom Colleg,India, Assistant professor, Department of Mathematics
College of Sciences and Humanities ,Osmania University, India,Prince Sattam bin
Abdulaziz University,Saudi Arabia

Abstract— Let $G = (V, E)$ be a finite simple and undirected graph without isolated vertices. An undirected graph $G_{m,n}$ is defined as a graph whose vertex set $V = I_n = \{1,2,3, \dots\}$ where $u, v \in V$ are adjacent if and only if $u \neq v$ and $u+v$ is not divisible by m where m belongs to natural numbers greater than 1. A subset D of V is a pitchfork dominating set if every vertex $v \in D$ dominates at least j and at most k vertices of $V - D$, for any non-negative integers j and k . A subset D^{-1} of $V - D$ is an inverse pitchfork dominating set with respect to D if it is a dominating set. The minimum cardinality of all pitchfork dominating sets in G is called the pitchfork domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma_{pf}(G)$. The inverse domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of all inverse pitchfork dominating sets in G . In this paper, an implementation of pitchfork domination and its inverse is given on an undirected graph $G_{m,n}$. Evaluations and proofs are given for $\gamma_{pf}(G)$ and $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G)$ in an undirected graph $G_{m,n}$ for different values of m and n .

Keywords— Pitchfork domination, inverse pitchfork domination, undirected graph $G_{m,n}$

Introduction

In this paper we discuss some variation of Pitchfork domination and its related parameter. The concept of domination in graph theory originated from a chess board problem. In 1850, Chess players were interested in minimizing the number of queens such that every square on the chess board either contains a queen or is attacked by a queen. On a chess board a queen can move either vertically or horizontally or diagonally and other moves of queen are invalid. C. F. de Jaenisch [7] in the year 1862 described this problem mathematically.

Apart from chess, Domination arises in facility location problems, where the number of facilities (e.g., hospitals, fire stations) is fixed and one attempts to minimize the distance that a person needs to travel to get to the closest facility. A similar problem occurs when the maximum distance to a facility is fixed and one attempts to minimize the number of facilities necessary so that everyone is serviced. Concepts from domination also appear in problems involving finding sets of representatives, in monitoring communication or electrical networks, and in land surveying (e.g., minimizing the number of places a surveyor must stand in order to take height measurements for an entire region). Part of what motivates so much research into domination is the multitude of varieties of domination. In [5-6], the authors cite more than 75 variations of domination.

There can be conditions on the dominating set D (D is connected, independent, a clique, a path, $G[D]$ contains a perfect matching, etc.) or conditions on $V - D$ (each vertex in $V - D$ is dominated exactly once, or at least k times, or the number of vertices that is dominated multiply is minimized, etc.).

The graphs considered in this paper are simple and without isolated vertices. A vertex $v \in V$ is called a *pendant* vertex, if $\deg(v) = 1$ and is an *isolated vertex* if $\deg(v) = 0$. A vertex which is adjacent to a pendant vertex is called a *support vertex*. For any vertex $v \in V$, the degree of v is defined as the number of edges incident on v and denoted by $\deg(v)$. The minimum and maximum degrees of vertices denoted by $\delta(G)$ and $\Delta(G)$, respectively.

Let $G(V,E)$ be a graph, a set $S \subset V$, is said to be a dominating set of G if for every vertex $a \in V$ is an element of S or adjacent to an element of S . A dominating set D is said to be a minimal dominating set if no proper subset of D is a dominating set. The domination number $\gamma(G)$ of the graph G is the minimum cardinality of a dominating set in G [3].

A subset D of V is a pitchfork dominating set [1,2] if every vertex $v \in D$ dominates at least j and at most k vertices of $V - D$, for any non-negative integers j and k . A subset D^{-1} of $V - D$ is an inverse pitchfork dominating set with respect to D if it is a dominating set. The minimum cardinality of all pitchfork dominating sets in G is called the pitchfork domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma_{pf}(G)$. The inverse domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G)$ is the minimum cardinality of all inverse pitchfork dominating sets in G .

1. Undirected Graph $G_{m,n}$:

An Undirected graph $G_{m,n}$ was first introduced and studied by Dr. Ivy Chakrabarty [4], some of the properties of $G_{m,n}$ given in [8] are as follows:

1. The graph $G_{m,n}$ is connected where $m, n \in N$ and $m, n > 1$.
2. $G_{m,n} \cong K_3$ if and only if $n=3$ and $m \geq 6$.
3. If $n=m-1$ where m is odd and $k=n/2$ then $G_{m,n}$ is a complete k -partite graph.
4. The graph $G_{m,n}$ is Eulerian where m is odd and $n=m-1$.
5. The graph $G_{m,n}$ is complete when $m \geq 2n$.
6. The graph $G_{m,n}$ is Hamiltonian when $m \geq 2n$ with $n \geq 3$.

2. Pitchfork domination in an undirected graph $G_{m,n}$:

Recently a new model of domination in graphs called the pitchfork domination and its inverse are introduced by Al-harere and Abdhusein [1, 2]. In this paper a new application of this domination types are introduced and applied on an undirected graph $G_{m,n}$.

Observation 2.1 [2]: For a path graph P_n and cycle graph C_n , we have: $\gamma_{pf}(P_n) = \gamma(P_n) = \gamma_{pf}(C_n) = \gamma(C_n) = \lceil n/3 \rceil$.

Proposition 2.2 [2] Let $G = K_n$ the complete graph with $n \geq 3$, then $\gamma_{pf}(K_n) = n - 2$. Note 2.3 [2] For any graph G of order n and pitchfork domination number γ_{pf} , if $\gamma_{pf}(G) > n/2$ then G has no inverse pitchfork domination.

Results:

Theorem 2.4: The pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$, where m is even and n is odd for $n < m < 2n$ and $n > 3$.

Proof: Let $n < m < 2n$. Let m be even and n be odd with vertex set $V = \{1,2,3, \dots, n\}$.

Case 1: Let $n = m - 1$.

By theorem 2.1 [8] the vertex $v_i = \frac{m}{2}$ is adjacent to all other vertices $v_j, j = 1,2 \dots \dots n$ because $m \nmid (\frac{m}{2} + j)$. So $D = \{v_i\}$ is a dominating set. Since v_i is adjacent to all $n-1$ vertices, it implies v_i dominates at least $j=n-1$ and at most $k=1$ vertices. Therefore by definition $D = \{v_i\}$ becomes a pitchfork dominating set with $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$.

Case 2: Let $n \neq m - 1$.

By theorem 2.1 [8] the vertex $v_i = \frac{m}{2}$ is adjacent to all other vertices $v_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ because $m \nmid (\frac{m}{2} + j)$. So $D = \{v_i\}$ is a dominating set. Since v_i is adjacent to all $n-1$ vertices, it implies v_i dominates at least $j=n-1$ and at most $k=1$ vertices. Therefore by definition $D = \{v_i\}$ becomes a pitchfork dominating set with $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$.

Hence from case 1 and 2 $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$.

Theorem 2.5: The pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 2$ with $j=n-2$ and $k=1$, for m is odd and n is even, $n < m < 2n$ with $n > 3$ and $n = m - 1$.

Proof: Let $n < m < 2n$. Let m be odd and n be even with vertex set

$V = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$. Let $n = m - 1$. Clearly, in this type of graphs each vertex has degree equals to $n - 2$. Let us consider a set $D = \{(v_i, v_j); (i + j) \neq m\}$. Clearly D is a dominating set since every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to some vertex in D with $\gamma(G_{m,n}) = 2$. Since $D = \{(v_i, v_j); (i + j) \neq m\}$ dominates at least $j=n-2$ and at most $k=1$ vertices. Hence by definition D becomes pitchfork domination number with $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 2$ with $j=n-2$ and $k=1$.

Theorem 2.6: The pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$, for m is odd and n is even, $n < m < 2n$ with $n > 3$ and $n \neq m - 1$.

Proof: Let $n < m < 2n$. Let m be odd and n be even with vertex set

$V = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$. Let $n \neq m - 1$. By Theorem 2.1[8] the vertex $v_1 = 1$ is adjacent to all other vertices v_j where $j = 2, 3, \dots, n$. So $D = \{v_1\}$ is a dominating set. Since v_1 is adjacent to all $n-1$ vertices, it implies v_1 dominates at least $j=n-1$ and at most $k=1$ vertices. Therefore by definition $D = \{v_1\}$ becomes a pitchfork dominating set with $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$.

Theorem 2.7: The pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$ where $m \geq 2n$ and $n \geq 3$.

Proof: From property 2.5 $G_{m,n}$ is a complete graph. Also we know that in a complete graph each vertex is adjacent to remaining $n-1$ vertices, it implies $D = \{v_i\}$ is a dominating set. Since v_i is adjacent to all $n-1$ vertices, it implies v_i dominates at least $j=n-1$ and at most $k=1$ vertices. Therefore by definition $D = \{v_i\}$ becomes a pitchfork dominating set with $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$.

Theorem 2.8: The pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$ where $m = n$ and $n \geq 3$.

Proof: Let $m = n$ and m, n be even or odd. Then the vertex $v_i = m$ is adjacent to all other vertices $v_j = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$ because $v_i + v_j \nmid m$. Let $D = \{v_i\}$. Clearly D is a dominating set. Also the remaining $V-D$ vertices are adjacent to each other, it implies by definition D has pitchfork domination with $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ with $j = n - 1$ and $k = 1$.

3. Inverse Pitchfork domination in an undirected graph $G_{m,n}$:

Here we study about the inverse pitchfork domination and apply it on an undirected graph $G_{m,n}$ which was studied in the previous section by choosing the inverse pitchfork dominating set with respect to the pitchfork dominating set in the same graph.

Theorem 3.1: The inverse pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 2$, where m is even and n is odd for $n < m < 2n$, $n > 3$ and $n = m - 1$.

Proof: From above theorem 2.4 Case 1, we get $D = \{v_i\}$ where $v_i = \frac{m}{2}$ as a pitchfork dominating set. Now from remaining $V-D$ vertices, we choose $D^{-1} = \{(v_r, v_s); (r + s) \neq m\}$. Clearly D^{-1} of $V - D$ is a dominating set with respect to D . Hence $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 2$.

Theorem 3.2: The inverse pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1$, where m is even and n is odd for $n < m < 2n$, $n > 3$ and $n \neq m - 1$.

Proof: From above theorem 2.4 Case 2, we get $D = \{v_i\}$ where $v_i = \frac{m}{2}$ as a pitchfork dominating set. From remaining $V - D$ vertices we choose $D^{-1} = \{(v_r); r = 1 \text{ or } 2\}$. Also D^{-1} of $V - D$ is a dominating set with respect to D . Hence $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1$.

Theorem 3.3: The inverse pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 2$, where m is odd and n is even for $n < m < 2n$, $n > 3$ and $n = m - 1$.

Proof: From above theorem 2.5, we have $D = \{(v_i, v_j); (i + j) \neq m\}$ is a pitchfork dominating set. Now from remaining $V - D$ vertices the degree of each vertex is $n - 2$. So we choose $D^{-1} = \{(v_r, v_s); (r + s) \neq m\}$. Clearly D^{-1} of $V - D$ is a dominating set with respect to D . Hence $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 2$.

Theorem 3.4: The inverse pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1$, where m is odd and n is even for $n < m < 2n$, $n > 3$ and $n \neq m - 1$.

Proof: From above theorem 2.6, we have $D = \{v_1\}$ is a pitchfork dominating set. Now from remaining $V - D$ vertices, we choose $D^{-1} = \{(v_r); r = 2\}$ where $v_r = 2$ is adjacent to all other vertices. Hence D^{-1} of $V - D$ is a dominating set with respect to D . Hence $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1$.

Theorem 3.5: The inverse pitchfork domination number $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1$, where $m \geq 2n$ and $n \geq 3$.

Proof: From above theorem 2.7, since it is a complete graph, it implies if $\gamma_{pf}(G_{m,n}) = 1$ then $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1$.

Theorem 3.6: The inverse pitchfork domination number

$$\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 2 \text{ if } m=n \text{ and both } m,n \text{ are odd}$$

$$\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1 \text{ if } m=n \text{ and both } m,n \text{ are even}$$

Proof: From above theorem 2.8 $D = \{v_i\}$ where $v_i = m$ is a pitchfork dominating set.

Case 1 : when m, n are odd. Now from remaining $V - D$ vertices the degree of each vertex is $n - 2$. So we choose $D^{-1} = \{(v_r, v_s); (r + s) \neq m\}$. Clearly D^{-1} of $V - D$ is a dominating set with respect to D . Hence $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 2$.

Case 2: when m, n are even. Now from remaining $V - D$ vertices we have a vertex $v_r = \frac{m}{2}$ adjacent to all remaining vertices. So we choose $D^{-1} = \{(v_r); r = \frac{m}{2}\}$. Clearly D^{-1} of $V - D$ is a dominating set with respect to D . Hence $\gamma_{pf}^{-1}(G_{m,n}) = 1$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

IN THIS PAPER WE HAVE COMPUTED CERTAIN INTERESTING VARIATIONS OF DOMINATION PARAMETERS SUCH AS PITCHFORK DOMINATION AND INVERSE PITCHFORK DOMINATION IN AN UNDIRECTED GRAPH $G_{m,n}$. RESEARCH IN THIS FIELD IS GROWING RAPIDLY AND ACHIEVING TANGIBLE RESULTS

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